

THE EFFECTIVE USAGE OF DIGITAL TOOLS IN TEACHING COMMUNICATIVE SKILLS

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Fozilbek Orzibekov

Lecturer of Samarkand State Institute of foreign languages

Abstract: Nowadays we cannot imagine our teaching and learning processes without application of digital learning tools. Digital tools are programs, websites or online resources that can **make tasks easier to complete**. For example, **a video or movie maker app** is considered a digital tool that can be used to help students create a movie to help explain a concept they're learning. Other digital tools and resources include: word processing documents or slide presentation software. A lot of these can be accessed in web browsers without needing to be downloaded, and you can access them both at home and in work.

The effective application of digital learning tools in classrooms supports to **increase student engagement, help teachers improve their lesson plans, and facilitate personalized learning**. It also helps students build essential 21st-century skills.

Key words: Digital tools or resources, effective usage, video or movie apps, student engagement, facilitate personalized learning.

Introduction:

Almost all teachers are using Digital Technology Tools to improve the classroom experience. Majority of apps, software, and platforms support communication, maintain collaboration, actively engage, and curriculum creation for learners in any context. Social media, online games, multimedia, and mobile apps are tools that both students and teachers can use to interact. Programs for editing digital materials and platforms, including Office 365 and Google Suite, support collaboration and resource sharing. Digital tools provide a way to implement text, images, audio, and video for an immersive experience. Some popular digital classroom tools include Chromebooks, tablets, and Airtame devices.

Main part:

Today teachers and students can communicate, collaborate and share with their ideas no matter offline or online by means of digital tools.

The majority of these digital tools allow us to do the followings:

- Messaging
- Video interaction
- Annotation
- Audio communication
- Educational gamification interaction
- Creating posters, presentations, diagrams, etc. together in real-time...

Digital tools are the perfect medium to give students varied ways to express what they know. Use these tools to give students ways to practice and build up their expressive skills (written or oral). Digital tools allow students to develop their expressive skills and demonstrate what they know using text, photos, graphics, audio, and video.

For students who may feel anxiety and stress when required to produce or share work with their teachers and their classmates, digital tools can reduce threats and support production of language. Language learners may feel additional anxiety about speaking in a language they are not yet fluent. With digital tools, you can provide support for language production prior to asking students to produce language, interact or complete assignments.

All students benefit from timely feedback. For students with disabilities and language learners, it can be even more important to provide ongoing support and mastery-oriented feedback as they develop their understanding.

For students who need support developing language skills, it is also important to provide opportunities to communicate and interact using the language. Digital tools provide ways for students to practice phonics or pronunciation, to speak, to record, and to express what they know in varied formats. By integrating real time (synchronous) and independent (asynchronous) opportunities to interact, you can also support language development.

Tool	What You Can Do	Ideas for Use Online	UDL Connections
<p>Video conferencing tools (Zoom, Google Meet, Facetime, Skype, What's App)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Meet in real time with audio, video, screen-sharing capabilities, and optional breakout rooms to create small groups. • Younger students may have to turn off the video feature if the district/parents do not allow recording students. • Consider recording all video conferences with students, especially one-on-one meetings for your and students' protection – just as you would leave the door open when meeting with a student. 	<p>Asynchronous</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Record yourself speaking for a listening activity for students. They can see your mouth movements, listen, and repeat after. • Can also be used as a screen recorder for providing input. <p>Synchronous</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Meet in real time with students to model a skill or process, teach a lesson by sharing your screen and using pre-created slides or other documents, or use the built-in whiteboard to draw out concepts or notes. • Use breakout rooms for students to meet and collaborate in small groups – consider pairing with a task in Google Docs/Slides to monitor work and provide support when you are not in the breakout room with them. • Use as a formative/summative assessment for student presentations, oral reports, etc. (individual or group) • Meet individually with students to conference, provide feedback, and answer questions. • Provide online mentoring/tutoring sessions. 	<p>5.1 Use multiple media for communication</p> <p>5.3 Build fluencies with graduated levels of support for practice and performance</p> <p>8.3 Foster collaboration and community</p>

Conclusion:

As it was told before, the digital tools are the perfect medium, which give students varied ways to express what they know. The application of these tools allows students to practice and build up their written or oral skills. Digital tools allow students to develop their expressive skills and demonstrate what they know using text, photos, graphics, audio, and video.

Students able to access learning materials and interact and collaborate with their tutors and peers online can enjoy flexible, engaging and motivating courses of study. Digital education can expand the reach of learning to communities who could otherwise be excluded and provides scope for rewarding, personalized and self-directed study.

THE LIST OF DIGITAL RESOURCES:

1. <https://www.watermarkinsights.com/resources/blog/top-5-reasons-to-use-digital-tools-for-key-campus-processes>
2. <https://www.d2l.com/en-eu/blog/advantages-of-digital-education/>